

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CHANGES OCCURRING IN THE ORAL CAVITY WHEN USING METAL-CERAMIC DENTURES

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ABSTRACT

More than 70% of the population of our republic aged 20–60 years has violations of the integrity of the dentition, and therefore the need for orthopedic dental treatment is growing. Long-term clinical observations have shown that base metals and their alloys, remaining in the body for a long time, have a harmful effect on it. The degree of impact of dentures on the tissues of the oral cavity depends on the quality of their manufacture and the physicochemical properties of structural materials.

Keywords: base metals, metal-ceramic prostheses, complications.

Recently, there has been a tendency to increase the number of patients suffering from intolerance to metal inclusions in the oral cavity (removable and fixed dentures) [8,9]. Treatment of patients using metal-ceramic dentures is currently one of the most popular and effective types of dental care. Complications leading to the lack of results from expensive treatment are pathological processes caused by the action of construction materials [1,4]. Their frequency has increased by 3-7.6% in recent years [2,6]. Despite the keen interest in the diagnosis and prevention of the above-mentioned conditions, this problem has not found a solution for many decades [12]. Studies concerning the toxicity of metal alloys used for prosthetics or their allergic effects have not clarified this issue [3,10].

Purpose of the study: Determination of changes that occur in the oral cavity when using metal-ceramic dentures, selection of a differential diagnostic method and development of a concept of pathogenesis initiated by orthopedic treatment.

Material and methods. For clinical studies, patients were divided into groups. Treatment of 20 patients of the 1st group with defects in the dentition was carried out using metal-ceramic dentures made of base metal alloys. Patients in this group complained of burning, pain in the mucous membrane of the mouth, pharynx, lips; metallic and sour “taste”, “dryness” in the mouth; “the sensation of an electric current passing through.” In 24 patients of group 2, metal-ceramic dentures (Cellite-N alloy) were also used in treatment, but they did not present such complaints. 26 people of the 3rd group had no identified somatic pathology, did not have dentures, and had no periodontal disease or oral mucosa. When examining patients, dental and additional research methods were used: determination of the difference in electrochemical potentials of dentures, pH of oral fluid. The quality of the orthopedic treatment performed was analyzed [7]. The electrochemical potentials of orthopedic structures in the patients’ mouths were measured using a pH-meter-millivoltmeter pH-150MA and a set of electrodes: platinum EPL-02 and

silver chloride EVL-1M3.1 [5,11]. The pH value of the oral fluid was determined using a pH-meter-millivoltmeter RN150MA using an ESK-10603 electrode. Results and discussion The main complaint of patients in group 1 was a burning sensation of the oral mucosa, which most often occurs within 1-3 months after prosthetics. Differential diagnosis of burning mouth syndrome in these situations presented significant difficulties due to the coincidence of symptoms of electrogalvanic effects, microbiocenosis disorders, and manifestations of somatic pathology. Somatic pathology in patients of group 2 was 1.6 times less common (53.6%) than in patients of group 1 (87.5%). In patients who complained of burning, pathology of the gastrointestinal tract ($r=0.206$) and endocrine system ($r=0.239$) was mainly observed. The role of systemic mechanisms in pathology caused by dentures is confirmed by its predominance in patients in the age group 50-59 years (58.3%), including women in 71.4% of cases. The average difference in electrochemical potentials between dentures in patients with complaints of burning of the oral mucosa was 53.7 ± 6.4 mV, 3.2 times higher than this figure in patients without burning syndrome (16.6 ± 1.2 mV). The diagnosis of “galvanosis” was objectively confirmed in 25% of those examined with an average potential difference of 102.8 ± 17.1 mV. The data obtained allow us to recommend a method for measuring the potential difference between the dentures present in the mouth of a given patient as one of the objective indicators of the presence of galvanosis. The relationship between the recorded potential difference and the severity of clinical symptoms could not be established. This confirms the hypothesis that in the development of pathology, the leading role is played not by local electrogalvanic processes, but by altered sensitivity of receptors against the background of the summation of irritations in the peripheral and central nervous systems. Next, we studied the acid-base balance of oral fluid in patients. Studies have shown that the pH of the oral fluid after implantation and prosthetics did not differ significantly from that in those examined without

dentures and was, respectively: in the 1st group 6.5 ± 0.5 , in the 2nd group – 6.7 ± 1.2 , in the 3rd – 6.8 ± 0.8 units. ($p > 0.05$). In patients with galvanosis, the average pH was 6.6 ± 0.3 units. The results obtained do not confirm the opinion of a number of authors about the obligatory shift in salivary pH in patients with galvanosis to the acidic side due to electrogalvanic processes in the mouth [5]. It can be assumed that it is possible to compensate for the disturbed balance of microelements due to the mineral and organic buffer systems of saliva. The majority (66.7%) of patients had no visible pathological manifestations in the mouth; only in 33.3% we detected inflammation of the mucous membrane in the form of hyperemia and swelling of the mucous membrane of the mouth, lips, tongue, and gingival hyperplasia. Thus, the research results showed that in 12 patients of the 1st group, in the pathogenesis of diseases caused by denture materials, there were combined factors when somatic pathology was combined with an increase in the potential difference, errors in the orthopedic treatment of 3 patients. The diagnosis of “galvanosis” without concomitant pathology was confirmed in 5 patients, paresthesia caused by somatic pathology as the only etiological factor in 3 patients; facial neuropathy and neuralgia in 4 subjects. In 2 patients the cause of the pathological process could not be determined. Based on the research conducted and a generalized analysis of the works of domestic and foreign scientists devoted to various clinical situations, we have compiled a diagram of the pathogenesis of pathological processes caused by denture materials. Analysis of the clinical symptoms of diseases initiated by orthopedic treatment made it possible to systematize them according to the criterion of the presence or absence of inflammatory processes in the oral mucosa, detected by basic and additional examination methods. This sign can become the basis for ideas about the pathogenesis of diseases caused by fixed dentures (materials), allowing them to be considered either inflammatory (traumatic, toxic, allergic stomatitis) or non-inflammatory (galvanosis, paresthesia) - dysfunction of the receptor apparatus due to sharply increased or perverted sensitivity of the oral mucosa. Thus, the prevention of stomatitis and paresthesia before orthopedic treatment should consist of expanding a comprehensive examination of patients in the following areas: conducting microbiological studies and biopotentialometry, monitoring oral hygiene, studying the somatic status. The next measure to prevent complications is general medical and special training of patients, including the replacement of fixed prostheses made of dissimilar alloys when the potential difference exceeds 80 mV. When choosing alloys, you should take into account the availability of a certificate for a structural alloy, carry out an individual selection of materials, and if individual selection is not possible, be guided by the position of the alloy components in the galvanic series.

Conclusion.

To reduce the possibility of inflammatory processes in the tissues of the prosthetic bed, attention should be paid to planning orthopedic treatment: compliance with occlusal requirements and selection of the number of supporting elements. It is recommended to include bacterioscopy of material from the periodontal sulcus and biopotentialometry into the complex of examination of patients with metal-ceramic dentures as part of clinical examination, which should be taken into account when drawing up standards for providing medical care to patients.

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